

IO-500

This is the official **ranked list**¹⁾ from ISC HPC 2019 [<https://isc-hpc.com>].

Please see also the [10 node challenge ranked list](#).

The list shows the best result for a given combination of system/institution/filesystem.

#	information							io500		
	institution	system	storage vendor	filesystem type	client nodes	client total procs	data	score	bw	md
									GiB/s	kIOP
1	University of Cambridge	Data Accelerator	Dell EMC	Lustre	512	8192	zip	620.69	162.05	2377.
2	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	Summit	IBM	Spectrum Scale	504	1008	zip	330.56	88.20	1238.
3	JCAHPC	Oakforest-PACS	DDN	IME	2048	2048	zip	275.65	492.06	154.
4	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)	NURION	DDN	IME	2048	4096	zip	156.91	554.23	44.
5	CSIRO	bracewell	Dell/ThinkParQ	BeeGFS	26	260	zip	140.58	69.29	285.
6	DDN	IME140	DDN	IME	17	272	zip	112.67	90.34	140.
7	DDN Colorado	DDN IME140	DDN	IME	10	160	zip	109.42	75.79	157.
8	DDN	AI400	DDN	Lustre	10	160	zip	104.34	19.65	553.
9	KAUST	ShaheenII	Cray	DataWarp	1024	8192	zip	77.37	496.81	12.
10	University of Cambridge	Data Accelerator	Dell EMC	BeeGFS	184	5888	zip	74.58	58.81	94.
11	DDN Japan	AI400	DDN	Lustre	10	160	zip	74.10	12.22	449.
12	HHMI Janelia Research Campus	Weka	WekaIO		10	3200	zip	66.43	27.74	159.

13	DDN	400NV	DDN	GRIDScaler	10	30	zip	59.49	13.55	261.
14	Google	Exascalcr on GCP	Google	Lustre	120	960	zip	47.23	23.06	96.
15	JCAHPC	Oakforest-PACS	DDN	Lustre	256	8192	zip	42.18	20.04	88.
16	KAUST	ShaheenII	Cray	Lustre	1000	16000		41.00*	54.17	31.0
17	National Computational Infrastructure Australia	Raijin	NetApp	Lustre	15	180	zip	40.92	12.89	129.
18	JSC	JURON	ThinkparQ	BeeGFS	8	64		35.77*	14.24	89.8
19	DKRZ	Mistral	Seagate	Lustre	100	1000		32.15	22.77	45.
20	DDN	Bancholab	DDN	Lustre	10	240	zip	31.50	6.33	156.
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21	Hewlett Packard Enterprise	GTO	Hewlett Packard Enterprise	HPE XFS	10	200	zip	26.21	19.57	35.
22	IBM	Sonasad	IBM	Spectrum Scale	10	10	zip	24.24	4.57	128.
23	Clemson University	ofsdev	Dell	BeeGFS	32	32	zip	22.02	8.55	56.
24	Inspur		Inspur	BeeGFS	10	400	zip	20.17	8.61	47.
25	Yanrong	YRCloudFile	Yanrong	YRCloudFile	10	160	zip	19.14	4.22	86.
26	HHMI Janelia Research Campus	Vast	Vast Data	Scale-out NAS	96	3072	zip	17.18	8.15	36.
27	Fraunhofer	Seislab	ThinkparQ	BeeGFS	24	24		16.96	5.13	56.
28	Inspur	TStor3000	Inspur	BeeGFS	10	400	zip	14.67	4.48	48.
29	University of Birmingham	BEAR-AI	DDN	Spectrum Scale	10	20	zip	12.54	2.97	52.
30	HHMI Janelia Research Campus	dm11		Scale-out NAS	96	960	zip	12.45	3.22	48.
31	Joint Institute for Nuclear Research	Govorun	RSC	Lustre	24	192	zip	12.08	3.34	43.
32	Queen Mary	Apocrita	E8	Spectrum	10	240	zip	11.73	4.73	29.

	University Of London			Scale						
33	PNNL	EMSL Cascade		Lustre	126	252		11.12	4.88	25.
34	SUSE	TigerShark	SUSE, Intel, Lenovo	CephFS	14	98	zip	8.38	3.58	19.
35	Clemson University	Palmetto	Dell	BeeGFS	48	48	zip	7.64	2.93	19.
36	CERN	Bytecollider		CephFS	64	64	zip	7.56	2.83	20.
37	HHMI Janelia Research Campus	nrs	Qumulo	Scale out NFS	10	320	zip	5.95	2.59	13.
38	PGS	Lustre on GCP	Google	Lustre	10	50	zip	5.70	1.91	17.
39	HHMI Janelia Research Campus	qflash	Qumulo	Scale out NFS	96	960	zip	5.32	2.80	10.
40	Queen Mary University Of London	Apocrita	DDN	Spectrum Scale	10	240	zip	4.36	1.26	15.
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41	SNL	Serrano	IBM	Spectrum Scale	16	160		4.25*	0.65	27.9
42	JIHT RAS	Desmos		BeeGFS	10	60	zip	3.55	0.51	24.
43	STFC	Jasmin/Lotus	Purestorage	NFS	64	128	zip	2.33	0.26	20.
44	Clemson University	Palmetto	Dell	OrangeFS	32	32	zip	2.31	1.93	2.
45	Nemours	nas6	DDN	GPFS	1	2	zip	2.06	1.39	3.

[Download shown table as CSV](#)

Radar Chart

Hover with the mouse over the edges to see the actual values. Note that the graph is scaled to the highest value.

Controls

Equation

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[Download complete data as CSV \[https://www.vi4io.org/assets/io500/2019-06/data.csv\]](https://www.vi4io.org/assets/io500/2019-06/data.csv)

Values with indicate that a value for the computation was missing.*

1)

That means only those entries that qualify according to the wish of the submitter are contained.